

This supplementary material provides detailed descriptive analyses supporting the global characterization of neoplasms in dogs presented in Phase 1 of the main manuscript. All analyses are descriptive. No inferential statistical testing was performed.

Table S1. Top 10 histopathological diagnoses in dogs with neoplasms diagnosed between 2021 and 2024, Colombia.

Rank	Histopathological diagnosis	Tissue of origin	Biological behavior	n	(%)
1	Mast cell tumor	Skin	Malignant	883	15.3
2	Mammary carcinoma	Mammary gland	Malignant	613	10.6
3	Lipoma	Subcutaneous tissue	Benign	519	9
4	Cutaneous hemangiosarcoma	Skin	Malignant	440	7.6
5	Soft tissue sarcoma	Soft tissue	Malignant	344	6
6	Histiocytoma	Skin	Benign	306	5.3
7	Melanoma	Skin/mucocutaneous	Malignant	217	3.8
8	Squamous cell carcinoma	Skin	Malignant	209	3.6
9	Trichoepithelioma	Skin adnexa	Benign	195	3.4
10	Papilloma	Skin	Benign	192	3.3

Percentages are calculated relative to the total number of dogs with histopathologically confirmed neoplasms diagnosed between 2021 and 2024.

Table S2. Distribution of neoplasms in the dogs in this study according to tissue of origin and biological behavior (2021–2024), Colombia.

Tissue of origin	Benign n (%)	Malignant n (%)	Undetermined n (%)	Total
Skin/cutaneous*	1,582 (41.9)	2,049 (54.3)	139 (3.8)	3,770
Mammary gland	9 (1.4)	614 (98.6)	-	623
Digestive system	216 (49.3)	214 (48.9)	8 (1.8)	438
Respiratory system	3 (75)	1 (25)	-	4
Urogenital system	103 (61)	65 (38.4)	1 (0.6)	169
Musculoskeletal	2 (4.9)	39 (95.1)	-	41
Nervous system	-	-	-	-
Endocrine system	-	3 (100)	-	3
Hematopoietic/lymphoid	10 (5.3)	178 (94.7)	-	188
Eye and adnexa	10 (28.6)	24 (68.6)	1 (2.8)	35
Other tissues	527 (43.2)	668 (54.8)	23 (2)	1,218
Total	2,462 (37.9)	3,855 (59.4)	172 (2.7)	6,489

Biological behavior was classified based on histopathological diagnosis as benign or malignant.

*Skin, digital pad, external auditory canal, conjunctiva, scrotum, lip, nasal mucosa, pinna, prepuce, vulva, and eyelid

Table S3. Distribution of cutaneous neoplasm diagnoses (c-CCE and c-HSA) by breed in dogs (2021–2024), Colombia.

Rank	Breed	n (%) c-CCE	n (%) c-HSA
1	American Bully	-	6
2	Basset Hound	1	3
3	Beagle	5	11
4	Boston Terrier	5	-
5	Boxer	5	6
6	German Shorthaired Pointer	-	1
7	Bull Terrier	3	11
8	English Bulldog	1	1
9	French Bulldog	4	8
10	Chihuahua	1	-
11	Cocker Spaniel	3	-
12	Dachshund	-	1
13	Dalmatian	-	4
14	Dogo Argentino	-	2
15	Fox Terrier	3	4
16	Goldendoodle	-	1
17	Golden Retriever	6	8
18	Great Dane	1	2
19	Siberian Husky	6	1
20	Jack Russell Terrier	2	6
21	Labrador Retriever	8	5
22	Italian Mastiff	-	1
23	Mixed breed	32	82
24	German Shepherd	3	5
25	Belgian Shepherd	1	-
26	Collie	1	2

27	Pinscher	3	2
28	Pitbull	52	237
29	Pomeranian	1	-
30	Poodle	5	1
31	Pug	-	2
32	Rhodesian Ridgeback	1	-
33	Colombian Fine Hound	1	3
34	Schnauzer	6	3
35	Shih Tzu	1	-
36	Springer Spaniel	-	2
37	Weimaraner	1	9
38	West Highland Terrier	1	-
39	Whippet	-	5
40	Yorkshire Terrier	1	1

Total	164	436
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“Not reported” category was not included in the analysis (n = 10).